

Predicting the long term fatigue behaviour of filament wound Glass fibre/Epoxy matrix pipes

S.R.Frost

Koninklijke/Shell-Laboratorium, Amsterdam
P.O.Box 38000, 1030 BN Amsterdam
The Netherlands

ABSTRACT

This paper presents the development of a failure criterion for Glass fibre re-inforced Epoxy matrix (GRE) pipes, including the allowance for damage development within the pipe wall as a function of applied load. Residual stresses induced during pipe manufacture are also included in the analysis. Based on experimental verification of the failure criterion for short term data, the failure criterion is developed further to provide a generalised approach for rationalising long term cyclic data. A limited amount of cyclic fatigue data for 3 different applied stress ratios is analysed using this generalised approach, with good agreement obtained between theory and experiment.

INTRODUCTION

The application of composite materials in the oil industry can offer significant cost savings by utilising their beneficial material properties, high strength to weight ratio and good corrosion resistance. One of the most commonly used composite structures is the filament wound Glass fibre re-inforced Epoxy matrix (GRE) pipe. The development of a design guideline for GRE pipes will provide a tool for engineers enabling GRE pipes to be used with confidence. Understanding and quantifying both short and long term failure modes are pre-requisites for the development of such a design document.

To extrapolate from short to long term behaviour the failure mechanism common to both times must be established. For short and long term tests, pipes fail through weepage, a uniform seepage of water along the pipe length. GRE pipes are constructed from uni-directional plies angled sequentially at $\pm 55^\circ$ to the axial pipe direction. The fluid path through the pipe wall is the combination of delaminations plus through thickness matrix cracks running parallel to fibres. Both delaminations and through thickness cracks result from the coalescence of matrix micro-cracks and interfacial debonding. Throughout the failure process fibres remain intact.

Pipework is subjected not only to internal pressure loading but also axial tensile or compressive and bending loads. This implies that the hoop to axial stress ratio within the pipe wall can vary significantly from the 2:1 ratio, i.e. internal pressure loading only. Therefore a failure criterion is required which is valid for short and long terms but also can account for a range of applied hoop to axial stress ratios.

The stress/strain behaviour of GRE pipes is initially linear elastic followed by a non-linear region to failure, first weepage than ultimately burst. The non-linear region is a consequence of matrix

cracking within each ply, the density of which increases with increasing load, with the non-linearity becoming more severe for higher loads. To define a failure criterion capable of predicting weepage, allowance for the growth of damage as a function of applied load must be included. This paper presents the development of a failure criterion including damage growth along with experimental verification. Based on this failure criterion a generalised approach for predicting the fatigue life of GRE pipes is proposed.

DAMAGE MECHANICS

The application of damage mechanics allows for the change in stiffness matrix to be quantified in terms of the amount of damage. For GRE pipes this damage is in the form of matrix cracking and is quantified in terms of density of matrix cracks. The stiffness matrix of the composite is derived from two components, the un-damaged stiffness matrix plus the damage stiffness matrix, i.e.;

$$Q_{ij}^{total} = Q_{ij}^{elastic} - Q_{ij}^{damage} \tag{2}$$

Talreja [1] has derived the damage stiffness matrix for a uni-directional, transversely isotropic, ply with matrix cracking orientated parallel to the fibre direction. In its most general form, Q_{ij}^{damage} , in the fibre direction, is given by;

$$Q_{ij}^{damage} = D^2 \begin{bmatrix} a_1 & a_2 & 0 \\ & a_3 & 0 \\ & & a_4 \end{bmatrix} \tag{3}$$

where D is a measure of the amount of damage. In total there are 4 constants defining the state of damage. Assuming that each ply within the pipe wall has the same damage state, then the stiffness matrix of the pipe can be calculated from summing the individual ply stiffness matrices, Q_{ij}^{total} , using classical lamination theory, Tsai and Hahn [2].

To simplify and reduce the number of damage constants, three assumptions are made which reduces the number of damage constants in Equation (3) to one. It is assumed that the following material properties are independent of the damage state;

- (1) - The Young's modulus of the ply in the fibre (subscript f) direction.
- (2) - The Poissons' ratio of the ply in the fibre direction.
- (3) - The ratio of the transverse (subscript t) Young's modulus to shear modulus.

Using these assumptions, Equation (3) simplifies to;

$$Q_{ij}^{damage} = D^2 \begin{bmatrix} \nu_f^2 a_3 & \nu_f a_3 & 0 \\ & a_3 & 0 \\ & & \frac{G(1 - \nu_f \nu_{ft})}{E_t} a_3 \end{bmatrix} \tag{4}$$

where ν is the Poisson ratio, E the Young' modulus and G is the shear modulus. Talreja [2] has shown that the crack density or spacing of matrix cracks, s, is related to the damage constant D, through the following relationship;

$$D^2 \propto \frac{1}{s} \tag{5}$$

Therefore Equation (4) becomes;

$$Q_{ij}^{damage} = \frac{D^*}{s} \begin{bmatrix} \nu_{fi}^2 & \nu_{fi} & 0 \\ & 1 & 0 \\ & & \frac{G(1-\nu_{fi}\nu_{ff})}{E_i} \end{bmatrix} \quad (6)$$

One damage constant, D^* , is required to completely define the damage stiffness matrix for a given crack spacing. Using Equation (6) with Equation (2) gives the ply stiffness matrix as a function of damage. Summing the ply stiffness matrices over the number of plies within the pipe wall provides the stiffness matrix for the pipe. The constant, D^* , can be determined by matching experimental stress/strain behaviour of the pipe under a specific loading condition to predictions. Predictions of stress/strain behaviour and failure of the pipe for other loading conditions can then be deduced.

EXPERIMENTAL EQUIPMENT

All pressure tests were performed using a multi-purpose servo-hydraulic testing machine capable of simultaneously applying axial, torsion and bending loads. Internal pressures within the pipe, using water as the pressurising medium, were applied using a separate pressurising unit. The axial load and internal pressure were synchronised through computer control to maintain a constant stress ratio, hoop to axial stress during each test. Each pipe was instrumented with strain gauges for axial and hoop strain measurement and a leak-detection wire was wrapped around the pipe to monitor pipe leakage. Pipes tested were commercially available 100 mm internal diameter, 140 bar (2000 psi) rated pressure, with winding angles of $\pm 55^\circ$.

SHORT TERM FAILURE

Figure 1 presents the measured hoop stress against hoop and axial strain for a GRE pipe under internal pressure with closed, free-ends. This test produces a 2:1 hoop to axial stress ratio within the pipe wall. Figure 1 is used to calibrate predictions from the damage mechanics model, which is also plotted. The elastic stiffness matrix components are calculated from pipe mechanical properties presented by Frost and Cervenka [3]. For the laminate calculations, it has been assumed that thermal residual stresses resulting from pipe manufacture are present. A temperature difference between cure and operating conditions of -100°C is assumed. To fit predictions to experiment, D^* was taken as 20.25, with a crack spacing of 1.65 mm at failure. This choice of constants, both D^* and s is consistent with those values quoted by Talreja [2].

Figure 1 : Stress-strain behaviour of a GRE pipe under an applied stress ratio (hoop-axial) of 2:1.

Using Figure 1 as a calibration curve for the damage model, a short term failure criterion for weepage of GRE pipes can be developed. The failure mechanism is matrix cracking, fibres remaining intact. From microstructural studies these matrix cracks run through the ply thickness

and are parallel to the fibres. Therefore, the ply stresses controlling failure are the transverse and shear stresses to the fibre direction. Figure 2 presents these ply stresses deduced from two data sources, Shell and UMIST/DRA [4] (University of Manchester/Defence Research Agency) for pipes with winding angles, 45, 55 and 75°.

Figure 2 : Ply transverse and shear stresses at failure. Data reduction includes thermal residual stresses based on $\Delta T = -100^\circ\text{C}$ and damage accumulation.

Also presented in Figure 2, is a best fit to data simplified failure criterion based on a polynomial representation of the transverse and shear ply stresses. The failure criterion is of the form;

$$\left(\frac{\sigma_{norm}}{\sigma_{norm, fail}} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\sigma_{shear}}{\sigma_{shear, fail}} \right)^2 - \left(\frac{\sigma_{norm} \sigma_{shear}}{\sigma_{norm, fail} \sigma_{shear, fail}} \right) = K \quad (7)$$

where $\sigma_{norm, fail} = 75 \text{ MPa}$ and $\sigma_{shear, fail} = 120 \text{ MPa}$ are uni-directional ply transverse and shear strengths and K is unity. Using this criterion, a comparison between predicted and measured failure envelopes, Shell and UMIST/DRA [4], applied hoop against axial stress is shown in Figure 3 for a 55° degree filament wound pipe. Also, included in Figure 3 is a simple failure criterion for threaded GRE connectors based on maximum hoop stress. The Shell data tests were performed on pipes with threaded end connectors.

Figure 3 : Failure envelope in terms of hoop and axial applied stress for a 55° degree filament wound GRE pipes.

The agreement between prediction and experiment, both pipe body and joint failure, is excellent providing justification for the analysis, i.e. including both thermal residual stresses and damage accumulation, plus the ply stress failure criterion. Figure 4 presents a comparison between the predicted and measured, ref. [4], weepage failure envelope, hoop against axial stress for a 45°

wound GRE pipe. The crack spacing, s , is taken as 1.9 mm. The agreement between predictions and data is good, providing further justification for the analysis.

Figure 4 : Failure envelope in terms of hoop and axial applied stress for a 45° degree filament wound GRE pipes.

Based on the failure criterion, Equation (7), and damage constants the stress/strain response of the pipe under other loading conditions is investigated. Figures 5 and 6 present predictions of hoop stress against hoop and axial strain for applied stress ratios (hoop to axial) of 1:2 and 4:1 respectively along with measured data. The agreement between predictions and experiments is good. In these predictions it is assumed that the damage state within the pipe wall is independent of the applied load, i.e. D^* is 20.25 and the crack spacing at failure, s , is 1.65 mm. For the 4:1 applied loading ratio, strain data is only available up to joint failure.

Figure 5 : Stress-strain behaviour of a GRE pipe under an applied stress ratio (hoop-axial) of 1:2.

Figure 6 : Stress-strain behaviour of a GRE pipe under an applied stress ratio (hoop-axial) of 4:1.

LONG TERM FAILURE

To predict the long term failure of GRE pipes under cyclic loading conditions use is made of the scaled stress variable defined by Frost and Cervenka [3]. This scaled stress variable for cyclic loading conditions is defined as;

$$\sigma_{\text{scaled}} = \sqrt{1 - R^2} \sigma_{\text{max hoop stress}} \tag{8}$$

where R is the ratio of minimum to maximum of the pressure cycle. Using this scaling, Frost and Cervenka [3] showed that for internal pressure tests, mean and amplitude variations in the pressure cycle can be rationalised. Assuming that the ply stresses can be scaled according to Equation (8) then a long term failure criterion for cyclic applied stresses can be postulated from Equation (7). The criterion can be derived by scaling the ply transverse and shear stresses and by defining the constant K as a function of number of cycles to failure, N and crack spacing, s, and is given by;

$$\left[\left(\frac{\sigma_{\text{norm}}}{\sigma_{\text{norm, fail}}} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\sigma_{\text{shear}}}{\sigma_{\text{shear, fail}}} \right)^2 - \left(\frac{\sigma_{\text{norm}} \sigma_{\text{shear}}}{\sigma_{\text{norm, fail}} \sigma_{\text{shear, fail}}} \right) \right] (1 - R^2) = K(N, s) \tag{9}$$

Cyclic fatigue tests were performed for 3 applied stress ratios (hoop to axial), 2:1, 1:2 and 4:1 on 55⁰ filament wound GRE pipes. In all fatigue tests, the failure mechanism was weepage. Note in the short term tests for the 4:1 applied stress ratio the threaded joint failed. To infer the damage state at failure, the Young's modulus and Poissons' ratio both in hoop and axial directions were measured at the end of each fatigue test. Based on these after failure properties, the final damage state or crack spacing is deduced, assuming that the damage constant, D*, is the same as in the short term tests, i.e. 20.25. Table 1 lists the inferred crack spacings from the measured after failure engineering properties. Also listed in Table 1, as a reference, are the un-damaged engineering properties

Table 1 : Inferred crack spacings from after failure engineering properties

Applied stress ratios	2:1	1:2	4:1
Crack spacing, s (mm)	5.5	5.2	2.7
E(hoop,undamaged) (GPa)	20.56	20.56	20.56
E(hoop,damaged) (GPa)	19	18	16
E(axial,undamaged) (GPa)	13.63	13.63	13.63
E(axial,damaged) (GPa)	12	12	11.5
v(hoop/axial, undamaged)	0.56	0.56	0.56
v(hoop/axial, damaged)	0.62	0.63	0.75
v(axial/hoop, undamaged)	0.37	0.37	0.37
v(axial/hoop, damaged)	0.38	0.38	0.4

The measured after failure mechanical properties exhibited significant scatter and therefore can at best only be considered qualitative. Further experiments are planned to reduced the amount of

scatter. However, the trends in the measured after failure properties are consistent, i.e. the hoop modulus after failure is always less than, whereas the axial to hoop Poissons' ratio after failure was always greater than, the respective undamaged values.

Based on the crack spacings presented in Table 1, fatigue tests results for the three applied stress ratios are plotted using Equation 9 in Figure 7. Figure 7 presents $K(N,s)$, normalised stress parameter, against number of cycles to failure.

Figure 7 : Normalised stress parameter, $K(N,s)$ against cycles to failure for different applied stress ratios.

The cyclic data from the three different applied stress ratios tests collapse onto the same curve within experimental error. By defining a normalised stress parameter, Equation (9), allows for the effects of mean and amplitude variation in the loading cycle along with the variation in the applied load ratios to be rationalised. Unlike short term weepage tests, the amount of damage as quantified by crack spacing, is a function of the applied stress ratio for long term fatigue tests. For the 2:1 and 1:2 tests the crack spacing at failure is essentially the same. However for the 4:1 tests, the crack spacing is significantly greater, implying greater damage. For all three applied stress ratios, the amount of damage in long term cyclic tests is less than in short term tests.

CONCLUSIONS

The short and long term failure mechanism of GRE pipes is weepage, matrix cracking. For short term tests with threaded joints for applied stress ratio of 4:1, the joints failed in preference to the pipe body.

A short term failure criterion is developed from ply transverse and shear ply stresses, accounting for residual thermal stresses and damage accumulation.

The short term failure criterion is verified from measured failure envelopes for 45 and 55⁰ filament wound pipes.

The hoop stress/axial and hoop strain response from short term tests for applied stress ratios, 1:2, 2:1 and 4:1 is predicted using damage mechanics.

A long term cyclic failure criterion is developed from the verified short term failure criterion using a previously defined scaling variable for ply stresses accounting for amplitude and mean variations in the loading cycle plus a normalised stress parameter, a function of number of cycles to failure and damage, crack spacing.

Fatigue tests from three applied stress ratios collapsed onto a single curve, but for the 1:2 and 2:1 applied stress ratio tests the final damage state was different from the 4:1 test.

Damage accumulation in terms of crack spacing is less for long term cyclic tests than for short term tests.

REFERENCES

1. R.Talreja, Stiffness properties of composite laminates with matrix cracking and interior delamination. *Engineering Fracture Mechanics*, **25**, 751-762, 1986.
2. S.W.Tsai and H.T.Hahn, Introduction to Composite Materials. *Technomic Publishing Co., Inc.*, 1980.
3. S.R.Frost and A.Cervenka, Glass fibre re-inforced epoxy matrix filament wound pipes for use in the oil industry. *Composites Manufacturing*, **5**, 73-82, 1994.
4. P.D.Soden, R.Kitching, P.C.Tse, Y.Tsavalas and M.J.Hinton, Influence of winding angle on the strength of filament wound composite tubes subjected to uniaxial and biaxial loads, *Composites Science and Tech.*, **46**, 363-378, 1993.